

On the Attitude Adopted by Thinking Towards Itself

When the surgeon-scientist looks at an fMRI, he thinks about the thoughts or ideas or generalities of thoughts and ideas within the patient. Thus, thought confronts thought. It is not a direct confrontation, but via instruments of measurement. What if thought could directly interface with thought – so far unheard of in the modern world. If it could, we would do away with sound/voice communication as well as other types. In communication we have Encoders and Decoders. In the presence of direct thought-thought interaction, what might be the role of Encoders and Decoders? A direct interaction would be like that of waves on the surface of a water body, generated by two separated bobbing corks. The region through which a wave passes is its “mind.” When two distinct waves superpose, *there* is when interaction occurs.

Thus thought-thought interaction might be a superpositive interaction. It could be constructive or destructive, to varying extents. If we take this “extent” of construction as generating a basis, a sequence of real numbers might be encodable in the temporal pattern. There may be a very few other choices of encoding. Thus, a message is conveyed to that mind which is engaged in such a superposition. Suppose however a mind has no waves for its surveyable extent. That is, there are no superpositions in progress. Such a mind is unfragmented. It is devoid of the “other.” There are no “messages” in it since the neutral degree of construction is held constant throughout. Things that don’t think could then be perceived in this clarity (ripple-freedom).¹ Spirituality is such insight. It is an insight since it is an attitude of thought towards itself which delights in its own absence. Juxtaposing ripple-freedom with the exchange of messages can be jointly or alternately pursued for maximum effectiveness in and out of the world of discourse.

Bibliography

1. G. W. F. Hegel, Lectures on Logic
2. Ken Wilber, The Spectrum of Consciousness

¹ Care must be taken to avoid the pre/trans-fallacy of Ken Wilber.